

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

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Digitising Temple City of India : Bhu, Bhuvan, Swar

Cultural Administration in Digital
India

Safeguarding the Tangible and Intangible of
Bhubaneswar through Digital Empowerment

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Table of Contents

Introduction	2
Orissa and her remains, Mano Mohan Ganguly, 1912	6
Cannons of Orissa architecture by Nirmal Kumar Bose 1931	9
The Hindu Temple by Stella Kramrisch 1946	12
Shilpa Prakasha by Alicia Boner & Sadashiv Ratha Sharma 1966	16
Classical Indian Dance in Literature and Arts by Kapila Vatsyayan 1971	20
Gazetteer of India Volume II 1973 (reprint 2015)	24
Digital Hampi: Preserving Indian Cultural Heritage 2017	28
Research Gap in Indian Digital Cultural Heritage	32
Conclusion	33
References	37

Introduction

In her introduction to Volume I of Kalaatattvakosa, Dr. Bettina Baumer states thus,

“The Indian arts, both in theory (Shastra) and practice (prayoga), are branches of a single living tree of Indian culture. They cannot be understood in isolation from other dimensions of thought and science, myth and ritual, spiritual and secular traditions. The underlying world-view has crystallized in certain concepts, reflecting the understanding of cosmos and man, of space and time, of form and structure, of the part and the whole, of body, senses and mind.”¹

It is but obvious then that the arts occupy an intermediate position mediating between metaphysics and physics, between spirituality and science. The Purusha Sukta gives a vivid account of the cosmic man and lays the foundation for comprehending the ‘human’, the anatomical and physiological, physical, social and cosmic man. ‘Man’, cosmic or human, has a defined structure with the parts and the whole again inter-related and interlocked. And a Hindu temple, in all its sculptural and architectural magnificence, represents a whole metaphysical conception and at the same time its building requires the science and technology of architecture and engineering, thus necessitating an indispensably inter-disciplinary approach.

The vast Hindu canonical literature on Devalaya Vastu and sacred geography describe the temple as a cosmic man, the ‘Purusha’. The ancient Indian text on Vastu Shastra (traditional science of architecture), the Mayamatam, refers the Vastu Purusha as the presiding deity of all land structures meant for temple or house. The ground plan, the Vastu Purusha Mandala is the metaphysical plan of the temple incorporating the course of heavenly bodies and supernatural forces.

The name Vastu Purusha Mandala essentially consists of three parts – Vastu, Purusha and Mandala. Stella Kramrisch, in her monumental work and certainly one of the most authoritative on Hindu temple architecture, THE HINDU TEMPLE, explains these thus –

‘Vastu is the extent of Existence in its ordered state and is likened to the Purusha, the Supernal or Cosmic Man, whose image is congruous and identical to the planned site.’

Purusha, the Cosmic Man, is the origin and source of Existence (Aparaa-prakriti) and is known to the world as the manifested aspect of Himself, the Paraa-prakriti, the immutable Supreme One. In his identity with the plan, Purusha is shown in his conditioned aspect. While Mandala, in general, denotes any closed polygon, the Vastupurushamandala specifically is a square which is its essential form. It could also be converted into a triangle, hexagon, octagon and circle of equal area and

¹ Baumer, Bettina Kalatattvakosha Volume I, 1pp

still retain its symbolism. Describing it as the magic diagram (yantra) and the form (rupa) of the Vastupurusha, Kamrisch further elaborates,

‘It is his body (sharira) and a bodily device (sharira yantra) by which those who have the requisite knowledge attain the best results in temple building, It is laid out in tabular notation as man (naraprastara) and site (vaastuprastara).

In the Purusha, Supernal man, the Supreme Principle is beheld. Beyond form and non-contingent, it is beyond description. It is known by intellectual intuition as residing in man, the microcosm, and in the universe, the macrocosm. Either is its place of manifestation. Man and Universe are equivalent in this their indwelling centre. Of this equivalence the Purusha is an image. In the Purusha, the relation of the Supreme Principle (Brahman) and of manifestation is seen as coterminous.....It is the site indwelt, and pervaded by the Purusha.....By its impress that piece of land, freed of all associations acts as primordial, undifferentiated substance (Prakriti).²

Thus within the structure of the Hindu temple, and in the particular context of the magnificent temples in Bhubaneswar, the intangible co-exists with the tangible, rather, one may say, the subtle yet all-encompassing intangible is ensconced within the magnanimous tangible.

And one is further reminded of the hidden power of this intangible character in the reflections of Nirmal Kumar Bose, a leading Indian anthropologist, on the styles of Indian temple architecture where he relates an incident when he came across a young man belonging to the stonemason caste in Odisha who was able to recite page after page from the shilpashastra from memory alone. Yet, he or his ancestors have never been called upon to build a temple for many a century. When asked why he had after all committed the shastras to memory, he explained with some amount of pride and tinge of sorrow that he had done so for a special reason. It was true people in general did not pay to artisans the respect or consideration which was their due. But if that neglect hurt them and led them to neglect their own craft and its sacred lore, then ‘the seed would become lost’. He hoped that some day men would once more learn to respect the artist and make use of the secret knowledge which men like him had preserved through many hardships.³

The land of Odisha is a thriving example of India’s exquisite cultural heritage – be it tangible, as observed in Orissan sculpture and architecture, or intangible, as in the rich legacy of Odissi dance and allied arts.

Within it, the city of Bhubaneswar is found to be a confluence of Hindu, Buddhist and Jain heritage boasting of some of the finest Kalingan temples. With many 6th-13th century CE Hindu temples, which span the entire spectrum of Kalinga architecture, Bhubaneswar is often referred to as a "Temple City of India".

Along with the old town, the region, historically was often depicted as *Ekamra Kshetra* (Temple City). With the diverse ranges of heritage resources, it showcases significant sacred cultural landscape components which have evolved with the support of available natural resource base and cultural trigger.

² Kramrisch, Stella The Hindu Temple Volume I

³ Ed. Vatsyayan, Kapila The Cultural Heritage of India Volume VII, Ramkrishna Mission Institute of Culture, Kolkata

Although the modern city of Bhubaneswar was formally established only in 1948, the history of the areas in and around the present-day city can be traced to 3rd century BCE and earlier. With Puri and Konark it forms the *Swarna Tribhuja* (Golden Triangle), one of eastern India's most visited destinations.

In India, dance has been notated for centuries through the plastic medium, tangible evidence of which we find in abundance in the sculptural poses of thousands of temple walls, in the carvings found in hidden caves and also in the manuscripts and paintings of different periods of time. So it is obvious that a very firm heritage of dance has existed in India from ancient times.

And, in the context of Odissi dance as an indispensable element of the intangible cultural heritage

of Odisha, the earliest evidence of which is found in the form of carvings found in the caves of *Khandagiri* and *Udaygiri* dating back to 100 B.C.(D N Patnaik), establish without doubt that Odissi is one of the oldest dance traditions in the world today. Born out of two ancient intangible traditions, the *Mahari* – servants of God who, consecrated to the deity as young maidens, sang and danced for the

deity alone within the temple's sanctum sanctorum, and the *Gotipua* – young boys dressed up as women who sang and danced in public propagating the Vaishnava consciousness of the union of humanity (the female) and the Infinite (the only male), Odissi, deeply impacted over centuries by the religious, social and political changes of its birth land Orissa, was reconstructed from extant dance treatises such as the invaluable *Abhinaya Chandrika* of the 15th century and the endless sculptural poses on the Orissan temple walls⁴ (Jiwan Pani), these serving as reference points of authenticity to the scholars and gurus who set themselves the task of identifying what was true to

the form, refining it and finally not only codifying the grammar and technique, but also devising a fixed repertory for the dance⁵ (DN Patnaik). Thus the current practitioners of modern day Odissi have a definite 'usable past'⁶ (Helen Thomas) relying upon which new dance works are being created today.

⁴ Pani, Jiwan The Tradition of Odissi Music (1960), article for Marg Publications

⁵ Patnaik, Dhirendranath The Historical Evolution of Odissi Dance (1960), article for Marg Publications

⁶ Thomas, Helen The Ephemeral Nature of Dance, article

In the course of my practice, performance of Indian classical dance and my study of Hindu temple architecture, I have come to realise that within the structure of Odissi as well as that of the Hindu temple, Indian philosophy and science come together in complete harmony as an organic whole. Both excel in terms of aesthetic sensibility as also scientific technique. And in the city of Bhubaneswar, one witnesses this coming together of art and science in their natural co-existence.

So the question is, how can these indigenous artistic and technological skills be preserved, popularised for, passed on to and made to appreciate by the coming generations. How can these be made accessible to people across nations virtually?

This is where digital technology must step in so that the generations to come across nations become aware of and appreciate the magnanimity and depth of these cultural traditions and skills. And this will be possible when cultural institutions are digitally empowered.

The focus of this research is to understand, assimilate and eventually implement how culture and technology can work together to drive audience engagement, boost the capability of cultural institutions, both public and private, and unleash the creative potential of technology. This in turn would facilitate digital conservation and promotion of cultural heritage, both tangible and intangible.

In this digital age, Technology allows cultural experiences to be more accessible than ever; whether viewing collections online, experiencing immersive theatre or purchasing e-tickets for productions. We can look at a painting, read a novel, discover the heritage on our doorstep, or listen to music at a moment's notice, on multiple platforms and wherever we are in the world. Cultural institutions, both private and are beginning to harness the potential of digital technology to engage audiences through new formats and mediums. They have a powerful role to play for audiences – particularly younger audiences – in the digital age. In the echo chamber of social media where content and commentary can be chosen to confirm existing views, cultural organisations can provide challenge, interrogate our opinions, reveal our history and support our sense of community.

The review of literature looks at treatises on Orissan Temple Architecture specifically and on Indian Art in general, written at different time periods and an attempt has been made to chronologically arrange notes from them to give an idea of the timeline related to the body of literature existing on this research and related areas. The conclusion, in the end, renders an analysis of the content of each text in the context of the focus of this research study.

Orissa and her remains, Mano Mohan Ganguly, 1912

To a student of Architecture, Orissa is important by reason of its being the seat of Indo-Aryan style in its purest form; here we do not notice the least vestige of foreign influence. It has maintained its native purity marvellously, being nurtured and reared on the very soil where it grew, without any extraneous aid. This is really a marvel in the History of Architecture, the like of which we rarely come across.

The Orissan style of Architecture indicates a definite style not hampered by any extraneous influence. That the Orissan sub-group of Indo-Aryan style of Architecture presents a continuous series for a period of 5 to 6 centuries lends an additional weight to its study.

Since the introduction of the tooth-relic into Orissa, we notice three following periods of architectural growth –

- The Buddhist and Jaina period
- The Shaiva period
- The Vaishnava and Shaurya period

The Buddhist and jain period is characterised by cave temples. The Buddhist influence is noticed from the 5th century BC down to the 5th or 6th century AD, the Shaiva from 5th or 6th century AD to the 12th century AD and the Vaishnava from the 12th century AD downwards.

The Temples of Bhubanesvara

The temples of the locality in and near Bhubanesvara are older than those at Puri or Konarka; and those at Bhubanesvara belong to various stages extending over several centuries, hence they are divided into several classes or groups based on their chronological order.

There are some five hundred temples scattered here and there in and near Bhubanesvara, and it is impossible to describe them within a small compass of this book. Ganguly contents himself with the description of only a few out of the list given below.

- Muktesvara
- Kedareshvara

- Siddhesvara
- Parashuramesvara
- Gauri
- Uttaresvara
- Bhaskaresvara
- Rajarani
- Nayakesvara
- Brahmesvara
- Meghesvara
- Ananta Vasudeva
- Gopalini
- Savitri
- Lingaraja
- Sarideul
- Somesvara
- Yamesvara
- Kotitirthesvara
- Hatakesvara
- Kapalamochani
- Ramesvara
- Gosahasresvara
- Sisiresvara
- Kapilesvara
- Varunesvara

- Chakresvara and many others

The temple of Muktesvara may be styled the epitome of Orissan architecture showing all that is best in it. It may be appropriately called a dream in sandstone adapting the immortal phraseology of Colonel Sleeman regarding Taj Mahal. It seems that the artist must have bestowed all his care and skill to make it a perfect, well proportioned model of Orissan architecture.

The temple of Parashuramesvara one of the oldest at Bhubanesvara is unique from the architectural point of view, being a departure from the usual type. What strikes the most casual observer at first sight is the Jagamohana which does not present the usual shape of a stepped pyramid towering a cube. The plan of the Jagamohana is rectangular, the larger side being in the same line with the face of the Vimana. This temple, unlike those of the usual type, faces the west. The interior of the Jagamohana presents the appearance of a nave, and two aisles characteristic of a Christian church, the roof being supported by two parallel rows of three rectangular pillars.

Cannons of Orissa architecture by Nirmal Kumar Bose 1931

The studies of Fergusson, Prasanna kumar Acharya, Manomohan Ganguly and Havell may be taken as representative of the four methods of approach which are generally followed in the study of Indian architecture.

Fergusson and others after him, like Cousens or Rakhaldas Banerji, depended principally in their researches on personal field-observations. Almost all that we know at present regarding Indian architecture has been learnt through this process; still, the method itself has suffered from an important limitation in the past. The workers from the west, as well as their Indian disciples, were trained in the schools of Europe, and as they were not in touch with Indian craftsmen, they lost the means of gaining an insight into the traditional point of view in regard to architecture. They did not know how buildings and temples were classified by the builders themselves, what distinctions were drawn between different varieties of temples, which were considered the finer points in building-technique and so forth. In other words, what was essential and what was secondary according to the local science of architecture was not known to anyone. This is the reason why, in some historical reconstructions of the Fergusson school, primary matters have given the place of importance to matters of secondary value.

The fact is that the master-builders of ancient India transmitted most of their technical knowledge to pupils by word of mouth. So they never considered it worthwhile to keep in writing such details as the methods of polishing or dressing stones or the means of transporting them to great heights and so on. These were left to the practical training which every architect was expected to undergo under the guidance of his preceptor. The craftsmen (silpins) therefore only recorded such information as they were likely to forget; such as the points of difference between various types of temples, details regarding their ornamentation, the relation between different parts of the body of a temple and so forth. But these details were kept in a sort of cryptic form. At one place, the numeral 5 or 7 might appear beside a term, *njis* may stand for 5 units of measurement or it may mean 5 times the length of some other object; only the experienced craftsman was expected to know what it really stood for. The canonical books of the silpins are therefore of the nature of mnemonic notes and are consequently unintelligible to one not belonging to the caste of silpins. This has been the reason why, inspite of the labours of the scholars, our knowledge of Indian architectural science has not advanced as far as might have been expected.

Architectural study in India was initiated in the year 1835 by Ram Raz in an essay entitled "Architecture of the Hindus." Ram Raz read the Sanskrit text of certain silpasastras with the aid

of local craftsmen and employed the knowledge so gained in analyzing architectural forms extant in the Deccan. A combination was thus effected between the craftsman's traditional knowledge, field-work and Sanskrit learning, and the results yielded were correspondingly of a very valuable character. In the year 1912, an engineer named Manomohan Ganguli, who was also a Sanskritist and a wide traveler applied the same method to an analysis of Orissan architecture. Ganguli had secured an Oriya manuscript on architecture, but having no parallel reading in his possession, he had failed to make proper use of it. He therefore analysed the forms with the help of local craftsmen and also applied his knowledge of western architecture to the task. In this manner he succeeded in restoring a large part of the traditional knowledge of ancient Orissa.

The present book may be taken as a continuation of the work which Ganguli thus began in Orissa. Several readings of the Orissan canons of architecture have been secured and studied with the help of local craftsmen. This has been supplemented by field-work done in different parts of Orissa and the neighbouring provinces. A workable restoration of the science of architecture in Orissa has thus been secured. When similar restorations are available for other provinces in India and the existing examples of architecture studied in their light, it will be possible to reconstruct the history of Indian architecture with some degree of certainty.

Position of the Naga

According to the silpa sastras, it is imagined that a great serpent (naga) lies encircling every building-site. Its body is divided into eight equal portions, namely the head, heart, stomach, navel, anus, knee, shin, ankle and tail. The serpent moreover moves round and round in a clockwise direction. Its-head lies at the eastern point of the compass in the middle of the month of Aswina. It takes a year to come round to the same point. It is therefore possible to determine, on any date, where the different limbs of the naga will lie along the boundary of the site. It is required in the sastras that the auspicious pillar should be posted at certain points of the naga's body in order to ensure goodluck. The orientation of the door is also determined by the lie of the naga.

The classification of temples

Salutations to Sri Ganesha.

Let there be no hindrance (to this undertaking).

Thus (begins) in the Bhubanapradipa, which was recited by the sage Viswa-karma in the forest of Naimisha, (a description of) the characteristics of palaces (meaning temples in the present case)... Now (we are) to know how many rafhak as characterize the (different) classes of temples. The Brahmin (is characterised) by nine, the Kshatriya by seven, the Vaisya by five and the Sudra by three rafhakas. If one builds an abaratha temple, which is Brahmin (by caste), then the manes of the person will dwell in the region of Brahman, the Supreme Being. If one builds a saptaratha temple, one's manes will verily live in the SuryaandChandra-lokas. If a Vaishya builds a pancharatha temple, (or perhaps, more correctly, if one builds a pancharatha temple), 'then one's manes will dwell in the region of the I^udras. (If one builds) a Sudra or triratha temple, then one's manes will dwell in the region of the Moon.

Bhubanapradipa ends with the following shloka:

The merit acquired by performing the Ashwamedha yajna or the Horse-sacrifice a hundred thousand times is equal to the merit acquired by performing the Bdjapeya sacrifice a hundred times. The same is the merit acquired by building a temple; the former may even be less.

From an examination of the temples of Bhubaneswar, it appears that all the temples which can definitely be assigned to a comparatively earlier epoch on the evidence of epigraphy or sculptural style, have a ham composed of three elements, viz. pabhaga, jangha and baranda. There are as many as sixteen or seventeen temples of this order in the village of Bhubaneswar itself. It is only in the later temples that we find the barn being divided into five portions, namely the pabhaga, the fatajangha or lower jangha, the bdndhand or the bond, the upavjangha or the upper jangha and the baranda.

The Hindu Temple by Stella Kramrisch 1946

An attempt has here been made to set up the Hindu temple conceptually, from the foundation to its finial. Its structure is rooted in Vedic tradition, and primeval modes of building have contributed their shapes. The principles are given in the sacred books of India and the structural rules in the treatises on architecture. They are carried out in the shrines which still stand throughout the country and which were built in many varieties and styles over a millennium and a half from the fifth century A D

The purpose of the Hindu temple is shown by its form. It is the concrete symbol of Reintegration and coheres with the rhythm of the thought imaged in its carvings and laid out in its proportions. Their perfection is a celebration of all the rites enacted during the building of the temple from the ground to its pinnacle. Nothing that is seen on the temple is left unsaid in the verbal tradition nor is any of the detail arbitrary or superfluous. Each has a definite place and is part of the whole.

The Hindu temple is the sum total of architectural rites performed on the basis of its myth. The myth covers the ground and is the plan on which the structure is raised.

A pilgrimage visit to a temple is undertaken for the purpose of looking at it (darshana) with the sight of knowledge. Darshana is also the mine of the 'traditional points of view or methods of cognizing Truth'. The architect of the temple was not only a master of the 'ocean of the science of architecture'. Balanced himself in body and mind, he had to be versed in the traditional science (shastra) in its various branches, and as much in the knowledge of rhythms (chandas), mathematics and astronomy as in the conditions of different places etc⁷. The various arts and sciences had to be known for one and the same purpose, so that he could apply them in his work which was to be an image and reconstitution of the universe.

THE SITE

The architect, Sthapati is the foremost of the craftsmen (silpin), of whom there are four classes, Sthapatlu, Sutragrihin, Taksaka and Vardliakin, the designing architect, surveyor, sculptor and builder-plasterer-painter. These craftsmen carry out the instructions of the Sthapaka, the architect-priest, who has the qualification of an Acharya. Of the Sthapaka, the architect-priest who is to have the qualification of an *Acharya*, the one who knows the essence of the sacred texts – the Vedas and Agamas, Stella Kamrisch says,

“The architect of the temple was not only a master of the ‘ocean of the science of architecture’. Balanced in body and mind, he had to be versed in the traditional science (shastra) in its various

⁷ Samaranganasutradhara, XLIV 2-4 and Vastuvidya, I 12-15

branches, and as much in the knowledge of rhythms (chhandas), mathematics and astronomy as in the conditions of different places, etc (*Samaraanganasutradhaara* – a treatise on architecture). The various arts and sciences had to be known for one and same purpose, so that he could apply in his work which was to be an image and reconstitution of the universe.”⁸

THE PLAN

Vastu, is primarily the planned site of the building. Its shape is square as a rule and its full name is Vastupurusamandala. This name consists of three parts, Vastu, Purusa and Mandala. Vastu here, is the extent of Existence in its ordered state and is beheld in the likeness of the Purusa. The image of the Supernal or Cosmic Man, the Purusa, is congruous and identical to the planned site. Purusa, Cosmic Man, the origin and source of Existence (apara-prakrti), is its instrumental or efficient cause and causes it to be of His substance as its material cause (upadana). This is how He is known in the world, the manifested aspect of Himself, the Para-prakrti, the Beyond-Existence, the Avyaya Purusa, the immutable, Supreme One (Uttama-Purusa). In his identity with the 'plan', Purusa is shown in his conditioned aspect. The plan makes the site of the building in his image which is his form. The plan of the building is in the likeness of the Purusa, or of the totality' of manifestation. Mandala denotes any closed polygon. The form of the Vastupurusamandala is a square. This is its essential form. It can be converted into a triangle, hexagon, octagon and circle of equal area and retain its symbolism⁹. The relation of the Vastupurusamandala to the site-plan, ground-plan and vertical section of any building is similar to that of the tonic and any musical composition. The Vastupurusamandala gives the principle of all planned architectural form and the prototype of its various rhythms Vastu-sastra speaks of Talacchanda, Adhaschanda, the rhythm of the level and of Urdhvacchanda, the rhythm of the elevation implying the proportionate measurement which connects the ground-plan and the vertical section of a building. The Vastupurusamandala is the plan of all architectural form of the Hindus. The site-plan, the ground-plan, the horizontal and vertical sections are regulated by its norm. Originally and in practice the site-plan is laid out_ according to the Vastupurusamandala, and the 'general form of the temple' (samanya prasada) given in the earlier texts, rests on the Vastupurusamandala.

⁸ Kramrisch Stella The Hindu temple Volume I

⁹ Brihat Samhita

THE ORGANISM OF THE PLAN

The size of the Vastupurusamandala is of no matter. It is coterminous with the building site, or with the extent of the Prasada or of a minimum standard size. In it are laid out the positions of the several buildings to be set up on the site and also the positions of the buttresses of the temple. The lines by which the square plan is divided into small squares, the two diagonals of the plan and the "lesser diagonals", 4 or 8 in number, and drawn parallel to the former have a definite width, proportionate to the size of the plan. The width of the main diagonals in a plan of 81 squares measures as many finger breadths (angula) as the side length of the small square measures in cubits (hasta, Br S , LII 62-63), and the straight lines have one and a half times this width. Their intersection (marma, a vital, or vulnerable spot) measures one eighth part of one square in the plan of 81 squares. The division of the square and also the divisional lines themselves are measured in proportion to its total extent. No building, or part of the temple must be placed on these vital points. The archetypal measure (mana) of the line (sutra) is known as Prana, immanent Breath or Energy. By it is measured the width of the outline of one square in an 'ardha-ksetra' (half field) of 360 squares ('Kamikagama', XVIII 8). This half field of 360 units is part of a wider extent. The whole field has 720 units (8 x 9 x 10), or, if 360 is multiplied by 72, or 9x8, which are the side lengths of the two types of the Vastupurusamandala, the number 25920 results which is the number of years in the period of the precession of the equinoxes. From Ayodhya, the impregnable stronghold of the gods, with its 8 Cakras and 9 doors, the whole field of 720 days and nights of the year is extended which is one of the units of cyclical time in the Vastumandala. Prana, the breath of life, immanent Breath, in man, the microcosm, is one in principle with Brahman (Sankaracarya, comm 'Brahma Sutra', III 2 7). In deep sleep (susupti) all the faculties of knowledge, sensation and action are withdrawn in Prana. Prana governs and is manifest in the vital functions of breathing, etc , which are called Vayu, vital activity. In the 'Kamikagama' the lines (sutra) are measured in terms of Prana and Vayu as archetypal measures. The Breath of life, immanent Breath, in the functions of breathing, etc , is the network that holds together the 'body' of the Vastumandala. In its duration it lies extended. The immanent breaths (prana) are the immortal parts of the body. With them, drawn in a network of lines, the body of the Vastupurusa lasts as long as the present aeon (kalpa).

The living breath of Vastupurusa would thus be seen to permeate the total structure.

The square Vastupurusamandala, it has been shown, faces the four directions. Its borders are occupied by the 8 regents of the cardinal and of the intermediate points. At the same time this square diagram of the earth, ordered by time, in its extent, coincides in the mandala, with the Ecliptic, in its border are accommodated the planets and the stars, and the movements of sun and moon. The Vastumandala is the place of manifestation, it shows the order that rules over it, cyclical time on earth, is occupied in its entire extent, by the Vastupurusa. The Vastumandala

indeed, is the Vastupurusa. His coming to earth and his identity are described in several versions, in all of them, the whole square field is the Vastupurusa whose body is one with the presence and actions of the 45 Vedic gods, stationed in the Vastupurusamandala, which is their yantra, the means of realising and the symbol of cosmic order on earth, its centre is the Brahmasthana, and its superstructure is the temple.

PLAN AND SUPERNAL MAN

The Vastupurusamandala is the magic diagram (yantra) and the form (rupa) of the Vastupurusa. It is his body (sarira) and a bodily device (sarira yantra) by which those who have the requisite knowledge attain the best results in temple building. It is laid out in tabular notation as man and site (naraprastara, vastuprastara). In the Purusa, Supernal man, the Supreme Principle is beheld. Beyond form and non-contingent, it is beyond description. It is known by intellectual intuition as residing in man, the microcosm, and in the universe, the macrocosm. Either is its place of manifestation. Man and Universe are equivalent in this their indwelling centre. Of this equivalence the Purusa is an image. In the Purusa, the relation of the Supreme Principle (Brahman) and of manifestation is seen as coterminous.

The ground plan of the temple, whatever may be its variations, is analogous to the Vastupurusamandala and retains in its rhythmic order proceeding from the centre and in the modulations of its perimeter, the knowledge of the Vastupurusa in all his parts. The rhythm (chandas) of the ground plan is domed from the order in the Vastumandala. The relation of sacred architecture to the Vastupurusa-mandala is reflected moreover in the sculptures on its walls, their iconography is essentially an iconometry (talamuna). The distinctiveness of the sculptures rests upon their proportion and positions, their merit is in their form and results from a supererogation in the correct execution of the rules. It exceeds the rules by intensifying their raison d'etre. To this excess of application is granted an immediate realisation, possible only where the knowledge is perfect. Its possession shows a freedom through which the grace of the Lord (anugraha) becomes impressed on the work. It is in the 'readiness' (pratyutpanna) which distinguishes the inspired craftsmen whose competence has become effortless. On the firm basis of iconometrical structure, itself correlated to and in continuation of the proportion of the temple, the many images have their place assigned to them as parts of the body of the building, their movements too and the relatedness of form in the single figures are similarly assigned.

Shilpa Prakasha by Alice Boner & Sadashiv Ratha Sharma 1966

The author of this text, who gives his name as Ramachandra Bhattaraka was an Orissan architect living in a tantric village on the banks of Mushali river and enjoying the patronage of one Raja Veeravarman of Airavata Mandala. As a follower of the Kaulachara doctrine he worshipped Jagannatha under the name of Dakshina Kalika. He frequently mentions the Saudhikagama as the source of his knowledge and his authority. This seems to refer to a tantric school of architecture, of which not much is known today, and on which this text gives valuable information.

The Saudhikagama was apparently based on tantric doctrines and the Shilpa Prakasha is entirely imbued with this doctrine. (Boner & Sharma)

A distinctive feature of S.P. is the method followed in the outlay of the ground plan of temple and mukhashala, starting from the centre of the garbhagrha, and growing outwards in geometrical proportions based on units of measurement underlying the grabhagrha. Under the grabhagrha a Yogini yantra has to be consecrated, which also does not occur in other Shilpa Shastras.

The Orissan temples have all one characteristic in common, in that they are divided into vertical sections running from the base to the top of the shikhara and are called rathas or paagas. These are separated from one another by deep chases called Khaandis in Oriya and Vishraantisthalas in Sanskrit which correspond to what in Rajasthani architecture is called Salilaantara. In front of the entrance of temple and mukhashaala there are invariably round steps called Nandaavarta, which occur also in shrines and stupas of South India and Ceylon and there are called Chandrashila (moonstones).

Another very important feature of medieval temple architecture, especially in Orissa, was the Vajramastaka, of which S.P. gives detailed technical description. It began to emerge in the later Gupta period, as a round gavaaksha-window, dominated or not by a lion-face, and was appropriately called 'graasa' or 'keertimukha', the latter term being derived from the sun-windows or openings (mukha) of a chaitya hall rock excavation (keerti). This round window with a lion-head on top on the face of cave-shrines was gradually conventionalised into a decorative motif applied to the front of the temples.

While other Shilpa shastras take a bird's eye view of the architecture of various regions and times, the author of S.P. limits himself strictly to his own time and place, although he fully acknowledges the authority of old scriptures.

The very word keerti, which originally meant a rock-excavation or a chaitya-hall, as in the Traikootaka inscription of 493 AD, is used here in the sense of temple. The author lays great stress on another feature which is the lion-figure and describes four types in detail. Two types of kalashas are also mentioned, the one in the form of a yupa or sacrificial post for Devi temples, and the other in the form of a full water-vessel for Shiva or Vishnu temples. One of the temples described in the S.P. is particularly noteworthy, because it bears a Buddhist name, and although being a Hindu temple points back to the Buddhist tradition, which prevailed in Orissa down to the 12th century AD. The followers of Saudhikaagama call this type of temple the Manjushri. In the chapter on the vimaana the author also makes a cogent and explicit defence of the amorous sculptures (Kaamakalaabandha). Its style is pure and attains to philosophical heights, while frankly declaring that these motifs are in accordance with Kaulachara rites. The author makes an interesting distinction between the Keli bandha and the Mithuna bandhas, the former ones denoting mere love-play, while the latter may depict Veeraachara rites or sexual union.

This important treatise on Shilpa Shastra ends with glowing tributes to the merit of building temples, and says that this is equal to the Raajasuya (coronation of the King) or to a Soma sacrifice. It also eulogises the Shilpa-Shastras descended from Vishwakarma which have kept the science of Shilpa burning through the ages.

The form of the Hindu temple responds more than that of any other sanctuary to the designation: Devaalaya (abode of God), because it is not, like the Christian church or the Mahomedan masjid built to accommodate an assembly of worshippers for community prayers and rituals. It is built solely and exclusively to house the symbol or image of a divinity, as the outer shell, enveloping and protecting that sacred core which is kept in intimate seclusion in the darkness of the inner shrine. This inner chamber is so small that it can offer place only to individual puja and worship. It lies embedded in extremely massive walls with no windows, receiving sparse light from the only door in front, that gives access to the shrine.

The Hindu temple, in a way, still partakes of the character of the cave sanctuary, which may have been its earliest form. Its inner shrine is often reminiscent of a dark mountain cavern, while the massive tower above is akin to the mountain, into which the cavern is dug.

When the Hindu temple provides a hall for worshippers, it is always built as a separate body, different in shape and attached to the front of the entrance by a narrow passage. The text of Shilpa Prakasha, describing a temple with a mukhashala, calls the main temple the bridegroom and the hall for the worshippers the bride. Divinity is here seen in the aspect of the heavenly Bridegroom, towards which the soul of the worshipper is drawn in lifelong love and devotion. This is a symbolism known in every form of Bhakti worship in India, pre-eminently so in the worship of Krishna. But it is known also in the Christian liturgy, where Christ figures as the

divine Bridegroom and the congregation of the faithful as the bride, or in psalms of David, where the relationship between Jehovah and his devotees is that between the lover and his beloved. Here this image is directly translated into architectural terms.

The temple is a hierarchical structure in the likeness of the Universe which contains in its vertical elevation an image of the three worlds, *bhuu*, *bhuvar*, *sva*. The foundation anchored in the ground is *Bhuu*, the Earth, the vertical body of the temple is *Bhuvar*, the Ether or Middle Space, and the towering *shikhara* represents *Sva* or Heaven. The first is the region of the *Pitrs*, the Ancients, the Forefathers, the second is the region of *Man*, and the third the region of the *Devas*. While divinity dwells alone at the centre of the bare, dark sanctuary, the cosmos displays all its variegated forms in the light of day on the outer walls. This is in accordance with the metaphysical vision underlying all Hindu Cosmogonies. The *Paramaatman* is not separate and above the sensible universe, but constitutes its very core and centre. From this very centre he throws forth, interwoven into one another, the endless universes and the eternal cycles of creation and dissolution. Thus the temple is an image, not only of the spiritual worlds, but of all manifestation, from the dark underworlds of subconscious life through the twilight world of man to the bright heavenly world of the *devas*. It draws no line division between the terrestrial, the semi-divine and the divine, but disposes them on ascending planes, and thus traces the way to *dharma* and *sadhana*, the way of ascent from the subconscious, vital spheres of physical life to the awakened illumined spheres of the spirit.¹⁰

The Hindu temple is also considered as the image of the *Mahaapurusha* who “on every side pervading earth, he fills a space ten fingers wide” (*Rigveda*, X.90, transl. by Griffith). He is the Cosmic Man, on whose body the entire creation is displayed, with all its material, vital, pranic and spiritual forces. This entire display is based and depends on the narrow inner space, ten fingers wide, the heart of *Purusha*, the sanctuary of the temple.

In medieval architectural texts, like the *Agni Purana*, the *Ishaanashivagurudevapaddhati* and others this symbolism is elaborated in a realistic manner. Every part of the temple is given some iconographic significance, detailed as the various members and organs of the *Mahapurusha*'s body, or described as the seat of the various divine powers dependent on the divinity of the shrine. In this way the entire temple becomes, in analogy to the image or symbol contained in the sanctuary, the manifested form of divinity, containing all levels of existence, all substances, *tattvas* and *bhutas*, from Earth to Ether, and its structure reaches from the underworlds up to the abode of the absolute, supreme, changeless Essence.

Following up the conception of a universe in effigy along the entire body of the temple, the various structural parts and their functions gain a deeper significance. The texts of the *Shilpa*

¹⁰ See Stella Kramrisch: op. cit. p 179 ff.

Prakasha, although it describes a temple form other than that of the Mahapurusha pattern – a Rekha-temple with a single straightlined shikhara – gives many valuable clues to the meaning and interpretation of the various form-elements, in the yantras underlying all parts of the building, as well as nomenclature of the various structural elements and in the character of the ornaments. The text itself only rarely offers explanations of the yantras or other parts, it may be because it was addressed to initiates who had full knowledge of these things. But the inner sense can be investigated with the help of analogies, of references in other texts and of conceptions grounded in traditional knowledge.

The book begins, significantly enough, with an invocation to Visvakarman, the Creator of the Universe. He who created the immeasurable Cosmos is requested to assist in building this small universe of the temple in its likeness. In the dhyaana he is described as holding measuring rod and thread, chisel and mallet in his four hands. He, the Creator, not only lays out the plan of the universe according to measure and number, but also fills it with the profuse, luxuriant life of all its forms, mineral, vegetal and animal, material and spiritual. He is the prototype and model of the temple-builder, who also unites in his single person, the architect, the priest and the sculptor. His help and inspiration are required for this great work. The instruments that Visvakarman holds in his hands are equally divine. They represent his power, his Shakti, to speak in tantric terms as our text, and therefore are invoked under the name of Kaali, the female, executive power-principle.¹¹

Visvakarman and Kali are the presiding divinities, activating the construction of the temple, this universe on a reduced scale.

¹¹ Even today the Sthapatis of Orissa offer worship to their instruments in the form of Kaalika. This, which is called Saajaa Puja is performed once a year during the last four days of the autumn Durga Puja

Classical Indian Dance in Literature and Arts by Kapila Vatsyayan 1971

‘King Vajra requests Sage Markandeya to accept him as his disciple and teach him the art of icon-making, so that he may worship the deities in their proper forms. The sage replies that one cannot understand the principles of image-making without a knowledge of painting. The king wishes for instruction in this art and is told that, unless he is accomplished as a dancer, he cannot grasp even the rudiments of painting. The king requests that he be taught dancing, whereupon the sage replies that, without a keen sense of rhythm or a knowledge of instrumental music, proficiency in dance is impossible. Once again the king requests that he be taught these subjects; to which the sage replies that a mastery of vocal music is necessary before one can be proficient in instrumental music; and so finally the sage takes the king through all these stages before he is taught the art of iconography’

This dialogue between King Vajra and Sage Markandeya from the Vishnudharmottara Purana illustrates very well the inter relationship of Indian classical art forms and the crucial role that these arts have played in the creation of Indian classical dance.

Thus Once an intuitive idea had been grasped by the artist on the spiritual plane, he followed faithfully and rigorously the laws of arrangement of word, line, mass, colour, posture, sound and movement as laid down in the canons, all these rules having been designed to perfect the instrument of expression of the ultimate spiritual fountainhead and the Infinite spirit, each single detail of technique being significant only in so far as it was hand-maid to the central intuitive idea and the Absolute State. Had the technique of the Indian arts been merely a collection of technical rules, it would have been difficult for the creative artist to adhere to them so faithfully and so completely over a period of fourteen centuries. Also had the technical laws not allowed freedom of expression, experimentation and innovation, there would have been artistic revolts.

Classical Indian architecture, sculpture, painting, literature (kaavya), music and dancing evolved their own rules conditioned by their respective media, but they shared with one another not only the underlying spiritual beliefs of the Indian religio-philosophic mind but also the procedures by which the relationships of the symbol and the spiritual states were worked out in detail. Each art worked out an elaborate system for the presentation of the different elements of a work of art in a deliberate and well defined pattern. The more deeply we penetrate the technique of any Indian art, the more clearly we see that what may seem spontaneous, individual, impulsive and natural to the lay spectator is in reality well-considered, long-inherited, minutely studied and imbued with a highly symbolic significance.

The work of art and also the artist and the actor thus become participants in a ritual where the work of art is the yantra- the device through which the saadhaka or the artist sees the vision of the Absolute as much as the audience to whom the work of art is presented.

The arts of Indian architecture and sculpture also manifest the principle of multiplicity and unity on the spiritual, philosophic and aesthetic planes. Hindu architecture proves most powerfully that all art reposes on some unity and all its details, whether few and sparing as in the Buddhist stupa or crowded and full as in the Hindu temple, must go back to that unity and further its significance; other wise it is not art and fails to fulfil its function. Indian architecture constantly represents the greatest oneness of the self, the cosmic and the infinite in the immensity of its world design. All the special features of this architecture, its starting point of unity in conception, its crowded abundance of mass and design of significant sculpture, ornament and detail, and its return to the oneness, are ‘the necessary units of this immense epic poem of the Infinite’. Its technique lays down the method by which this infinite multiplicity can fill the ultimate oneness, drawing one’s attention to the tremendous unity of purpose and design which Indian architecture symbolises.

In terms of aesthetics, since architecture, more accurately the Hindu temple, represents heaven on earth, it arouses vismaya or wonder and leads to the aesthetic experience of adbhuta.

Indian sculpture like Indian architecture springs from a deep spiritual realisation of the Divine and the Infinite. As Sri Aurobindo very aptly states,

“The divine self in us is its theme, the body made a form of the soul is its idea and its secret.”

Just as Indian architecture reveals the unity through infinite multiplicity, Indian sculpture embodies the spirit and soul of the cosmic Infinite in the form and body of the particular, the impersonal individual which in turn suggests the cosmic and the Infinite. The religious and hieratic aspect of Indian sculpture is also vitally connected with Indian methods of contemplation, where the image is the diagram or yantra which the artist and the devotee alike contemplate.

As in music, literature and poetry, so also in sculpture, the Indian artist cannot and does not take the particular, the human or the individual, as his starting point. The human form, the particular attitude (bhanga, aasana, mudra), is but the vehicle of a soul-meaning, a concrete embodiment of a great spiritual power and of inmost psychic significance. The parts of the human form become intervals or shruti of music and the characteristics of these basic units are worked out in great detail in treatises on Indian sculpture. Character is portrayed through a knowledge of types in which particular qualities predominate which is facilitated by a systematic use of the physical postures, movements, turns and thrusts of the body corresponding to the moods. This relationship of the physical gesture to a mental quality, mood or state gives Indian sculpture its distinctive character.

The classification of images according to qualities (guna) into saattvika, raajasika and taamasika, the analysis of the human form in terms of measure (taala and angula), the categorisation of types of movement into four bhanga or deflections (samabhanga, abhanga, tribhanga and atibhanga) and the enumeration of images according to their postures (aasana), have to be understood and evaluated with full realisation of the final function which any piece of sculpture was designed to fulfil.

In terms of technique, Hindu sculpture faithfully abides by an elaborate and beautiful system of proportions, that is used constantly to model different types of images. The sculptor combines the basic units of proportions according to well-defined laws in the same way as the musician combines the basic notes according to an elaborate system which has both an arithmetical validity and an emotional and spiritual significance. The division of the human form into taala and angula and the relationship of each of these to the different axes (sutra) is based on precise anatomical rules on the one hand, and laws of measurement on the other. With different aspects and moods of gods being depicted by employing different types of bhanga or deflections from the vertical axis or sutra, these laws of proportions at once become symbolic as also charged with motional expressiveness.

Comparative measurements have been laid down for the respective images in their various aspects:

The full human figure and the gods in their moods of serenity (shanta) or pleasantness (shringara) measure nine to ten units (taala), the heroic (veera) or the terrible (raudra) assume a height of twelve units, the fierce and demonic (bhayanaka) or the revulsive (vibhatsa) extends to fourteen units; goddesses and female figures in their different moods assume a height from seven to nine taala units. All types of characters can be depicted in terms of one of the five different sets of proportions, namely, the dashataala, the navataala, the ashtataala, the saptataala or the panchataala. The angula (like the shruti in music) is the basis of the taala, and can further divided and subdivided into yava, yuuka, likhyaa, romaagaara, renu, and anu(ray of the sun) as the minutest unit. Different texts work out the exact proportions of the human form in terms of angula and taala, taking one of the five sets of proportions for the total height of the image.

The human form is not only divided into taala on the basis of actual surface proportions, but also measured along various axes on different planes: the measures along these different sections guided the Indian sculptor in the making of images. Five principal vertical axes (sutra) are enumerated by the shilpashastra texts. The brahmasutra is the vertical axis or the imaginary line passing through the centre of the image and represents the direction of the pull of gravity. The madhyasutra is the medial line drawn from the centre of the crown of the head, through the centre of the chest, the navel, the knees, down to the inner sides of the feet. The parshvasutra is the vertical drawn from the side of the forehead, the cheek, the side of the arm, the centre of the thighs, the

centre of the knee, and the centre of the ankle-joint. The kakshasutra is drawn from the armpit, by the side of the hip and calf, and terminates on the fifth toe of the foot.

The three horizontal axes which are commonly used are the hikkasutra (the line passing through the base of the neck), the bhadrasutra (passing through the navel) and the katisutra which passes through the hips and the pelvic girdle.

The sculptor is thus provided with rules both for surface dimensions and for measurements along different vertical and horizontal planes and sections for every type of image. The six sets of measurements are termed maana, pramaana, unmaana, parimaana, upamaana and lambamaana. The maana is the measurement of the length of the body; the pramaana is that along its breadth; the unmaana represents the measurement taken at right angles to the plane in which the maana and the pramaana have been measured, i.e., along the axis of the thickness or depth of the body. The parimaana is the measure of the girth or periphery; the upamaana refers to the position of the different limbs in relation to each other, e.g., the measurement of the interspace between the two feet. The lambamaana is the measurement along the vertical axes.

With the alphabet of the taala (literally an unit of time) and the measurement along the different planes, the Indian sculptor models the different poses of the image, employing all the permutations and combinations of movement possible in a given space. Any movement whatsoever can be comprehended into the four deflexions or bhanga, i.e., the samabhanga, the abhanga, the tribhanga and the atibhanga only within the complex structure of the angula, the taala and the sutra measures. Further, when the shilpashastra discusses the exact points from which the brahmasutra has to be drawn in any particular pose and the exact distance of each limb or part of the human figure from this line, it is fully conscious of the corresponding emotion which these deflexions and poses will arouse.

Each aspect, mood or incarnation of the gods in the pantheon has its particular bhanga, aasana, sthaana, symbolic attribute, hastamudra, dress and ornament. The multiplicity of the presentation of the different movements and linear measurements and their fractions, deflexions and deviations of weight and distance, all coalesce into a single powerful symbol of a unified state or mood. The pyramidal structure which we have observed in drama and music is again obvious in sculpture, where the whole reveals itself through a multiplicity of technique and design only to return to the unity and the oneness of the basic state or bhaava.

The fascinating and overpowering quality of the most completely conceived technique is a distinctive feature of all forms of classical Indian art, where the smallest mathematical fractions and complex combinations of measurements all combine to suggest a unified experience on the psychical plane. The various aspects of technique move to form an artistic whole, corresponding physical and spiritual experiences merging in one overpowering symbol of an inner state of being.

Gazetteer of India Volume II 1973 (reprint 2015)

The Indian Shilpashastras recognise three main styles in temple architecture – the Nagara, the Dravida and the Vesara. While the Nagara style of temples are distributed over the greater part of India, of all the regional developments that of Odisha is one of the most remarkable. The Orissan temple remains nearest to the original archetype and has justly been described as exhibiting the Nagara style in its greatest purity. Temple building activity in Odisha is centred round the sacred city of Bhubaneswar. The typical Orissan temple comprises two main features, the sanctum sanctorum called Deul covered by the curvilinear tower and the assembly hall called **Jagamohana** in Odisha, surmounted by a pyramidal roof formed by a succession of receding platforms called *pidhas*.

Temple building activity in Orissa is centred round the sacred city of Bhuvaneshvara extending along the coast in the north-east and south-west and covering roughly the present area of the state.

The earliest temples in Odisha (Shatrughneswara, Pashchimeswara, Markandeyeswara), all more or less fragmentary, have close affinity with the archetypal design of the Gupta shikhara temple, each consisting of a square sanctum cella, triratha plan, surmounted by a tower of distinctly curvilinear contour.

Next comes the finely preserved Parashurameswar temple which illustrates an advance on the archetypal design in its anticipation of the future **Pancharatha** plan and in having in front a *jagamohana* with clerestory roof.

The small but exquisitely decorated Mukteshwara temple is perhaps the finest

monument of this early style wherein the sanctum cella and its *jagamohana*, now more organically related, stand within a balustraded court with an elegant *Torana* in front – two columns supporting a superstructure of arched shape. The sanctum is *pancharatha* in plan and the *jagamohana* with a pyramidal superstructure approaches more nearly the typical Orissan form of the *pidha deul*. With the corners carefully rounded off and the surface covered with exquisite ornamentation, the most significant being the delicate tracery of *caitya* window motifs, the entire effect is one of sensitive refinement. Belonging approximately to the 9th century AD, the Mukteshwara represents a mature expression of the Nagara temple style in Odisha.

The Siddheshwara, the Kedareshwara and the Brahmeshwara temples represent the transition from the Nagara style to the typical Orissan style, where in each of these temples, along with a *pancharatha* ground-plan there is a fivefold division of the *bada*, the *jangha* being subdivided into lower and upper sections by one or more course of mouldings (*bandhana*) running along its middle. With the rounding off of the sharp angles at the corners there was a tendency of the different sections of the *gandi* being transformed into miniature shikhara replicas (*anga-shikharas*), an early stage of which is recognised in these above three temples. In Odisha this tendency found emphatic expression in the Rajarani temple notable also for its rich exterior decoration.

In course of time the Nagara temple in Orissa assumed a particular and individual form characterised by fivefold division of the bada and anga-shikharas on the anuraha-pagas, besides

rampant gaja-shikha motif projecting from the raha-paga of the gandi on each face.

The majestic temple of Lingaraj represents this Orissan type in its maturity. Situated within a large quadrangular court, enclosed by massive walls and with a monumental portal in the east, the complex consists of four adjuncts extending in axial length from east to west, namely, bhoga-mandapa (refectory hall), nata-mandapa (dancing hall), jagamohana (audience hall) and the deul or the sanctuary proper. Judged as a whole, the Lingaraj temple is one of the supreme creations of Indian architecture, representing Orissan temple in its most brilliant expression.

Dated about 1100 AD, the Lingaraj supplied the norm to subsequent generations. Of the temples built on this model, few, not even the celebrated Jagannath temple at Puri, reach the massive grandeur and dignity of the Lingaraj.

However, the far-famed Sun temple at Konarak, built during the reign of Narasimha I (1238-64 AD), excels the Lingaraj in the nobility of its conception and the perfection of its finish. Grand and impressive even in its ruin, the Konarak temple represents the fulfilment and finality of the Orissan architectural movement.

Digital Hampi: Preserving Indian Cultural Heritage 2017

Indian artistic and temple architectural traditions give us rare insights into design, construction, proportion and scale.

Department of Science & Technology (DST) Govt. of India initiated the Indian Digital Heritage (IDH) Research Project in 2010 with the aim to extend the power of digital technologies to digitally capture, preserve, and restore all forms of tangible and intangible and historical knowledge. While archiving and disseminating digital representations of heritage artefacts and cultural traditions, the emerging multimedia technologies in computer vision and user interface design would make possible immersive experiences of heritage and possibly inspire young citizens to participate in similar projects around the country.

India is rich in cultural heritage with hundreds of important archaeological sites and rich traditions that need to be digitally preserved. The recent advances in digital technologies open up the possibility of creating rich digital representations of the heritage sites which can be preserved for perusal by world citizenry for the foreseeable future. In addition, digital restoration of damaged monuments, digitally conjured animations, and augmented reality representations of social life of past eras are intriguing creative possibilities today.

The objective of DST is also to build capacity in academia to create analytical tools for the art historians, architects, and other scholars in the study of the heritage of India. The goals of the IDH project were achieved because ‘best in class’ digital technologies ranging from laser scanning, 3D printing to mature and novel Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) came together and worked shoulder to shoulder with social scientists like art historians, archaeologists, architects, anthropologists and digital humanities.

Digital Hampi thus creates a new synergy between the art and the science communities for developing new frameworks and solutions to preserve heritage in digital space.

UNDERSTANDING THE MEANING OF HERITAGE

UNESCO categorises heritage into two broad classes – Cultural Heritage and Natural Heritage¹².

According to the UNESCO model, cultural heritage covers the following:

¹² Unesco (2003) Convention for safeguarding of intangible cultural heritage: 32nd session of the general conference in Paris 29 September – 17 October 2003

- a) Monuments: architectural works, works of monumental sculpture and painting, elements or structures of an archaeological nature, inscriptions, cave dwellings and combinations of these features;
- b) Groups of building: groups of separate or connected buildings which, because of their architecture, their homogeneity or their place in the landscape are objects of distinguished interest;
- c) Sites: works of man or the combined works of nature and of man, and areas including archaeological sites which are important from the historical, aesthetic, ethnological or anthropological points of view.

Categories (a), (b), and (c) together, in general, are referred to as tangible cultural heritage. The last category is as follows:

(d) Intangible cultural heritage includes oral traditions, performing arts, rituals, culinary traditions etc.

UNESCO further classifies some of these heritage elements as having “ Outstanding Universal Value”. Those heritage elements are distinguished by their cultural and/or natural significance, which transcend national boundaries and are of common importance for present and future generations of all humanity. Such elements are eligible for inclusion in the World Heritage List.

DIGITAL PRESERVATION OF CULTURAL HERITAGE

Affordances of the digital technologies have made digital media the ideal choice for the storage, representation, management and communication of cultural heritage. Tangible cultural heritage components like monuments, temples, groups of buildings and sites of historical significance can now be scanned, modelled and archived. 3D scanning is a technology for capturing spatial data in three dimensions. 3D scanned models provide the data for analysis and visualisation in virtual environments. These contents can be accessed through powerful search engines and database management tools. As a consequence, we create the possibility of disseminating the content through the World Wide Web to audiences who otherwise may never be able to access or visit the site.

Structural models represented by the 3D scan data accompanied by specialised imaging techniques required for faithful digital recording of colour and texture of the surfaces, particularly murals and frescos on the walls or ceilings, are necessary for authentic representation of the content in the digital space. This data, when linked with the structural model accounts for true modelling and rendering of the tangible heritage elements.

Digital preservation of intangible heritage involves not only capturing the data on digital media but also preservation of the knowledge and processes involved in it. Much of intangible heritage are, in reality, forms of embodied practice and its preservation in digital space means capturing the knowledge of the practice so that future enactment of the practice becomes a possibility. It is also important to link digital preservation initiatives for tangible and intangible to completely preserve the cultural heritage of a site. It would be pertinent to draw attention here to the fact that, a tangible cultural artefact may be related to intangible knowledge and practices in such a way that preserving the artefact without preserving the associated intangible heritage may result in loss of intellectual context. Therefore, digital representation not only preserves a digital representation of intangible heritage but also provides unique opportunity to present the heritage in an appropriately contextualised manner through walk-throughs in virtual spatial and intellectual spaces.

DIGITISING CULTURE – THE TECHNIQUE

Digitisation of the tangible cultural heritage in terms of 3D models has given rise to a relatively new branch of knowledge¹³ - 3D Cultural Heritage or Virtual Heritage that utilises information technology to capture or represent the data studied by archaeologists and historians of art and architecture. In addition to representation and archiving, 3D model construction enables the following:

- Measurement of the existing objects automatically using 3D capture technologies such as laser scanning or photogrammetry
- Reconstructive modelling of damaged or no-longer-extant objects by manual (using software like AutoCAD, 3D St Max, Maya) or algorithmic interventions
- Combination of captured and reconstructed models to create hybrids which are hypothesized representations of damaged artefacts

These representations are useful for cataloguing and documentation, public outreach and education, historical studies, experimental architectural and urban history.

Initiatives for documentation of intangible cultural heritage require an integrated approach for designing the digitisation scheme for the target domain, formulating the mechanism for extraction of the latent human creativity hidden in them and to study the importance of the spatial features in the process of their evolution. In the context of digitally documenting dance, typically dance performances are recorded in 2D video format. However, a 3D capture, using

¹³ Koller D, Frischer B, Humphreys G (2009) Research challenges for digital archives of 3D cultural heritage models: Article 7 17pp

Kinect or photogrammetric methods, would offer precise depth information for each dance movement. Dance analysis consists of movement analysis which attempts to describe, disseminate and interpret every possible movement¹⁴. We need to segment the sequence in terms of individual constituents in order to describe the motion. There have been several attempts to extract these features from motion capture data¹⁵. In Nrityakosha¹⁶, for example, an ontology-based framework has been presented for digital documentation of Indian classical dance.

¹⁴ Laban R (1966) *Choreutics*

¹⁵ Kahol K, Tripathi P, Panchanathan S (2004) Automated gesture segmentation from dance sequence

¹⁶ Mallik A, Chaudhary S, Ghosh H (2011) *Nrityakosha: Preserving the intangible heritage of Indian classical dance*

Research Gap in Indian Digital Cultural Heritage

- There is not enough research in the frontiers areas of digital heritage with special reference to problems of Indian context
- In the context of digitisation of cultural heritage of Bhubaneswar, one finds very little information
- Building of digital collections of heritage resources is found lacking
- Unrestricted access to multi-media digital resources and assets is unavailable. For example, the Book DIGITAL HAMPI costs INR 10,000 which is too expensive for any researcher
- Cross-disciplinary research in Indian cultural heritage and evolution to its digital form, though initiated by the Government, has not really found a firm footing till date
- Digitised form of treatises such as Shilpa Prakasha, Orissa and Her Remains, Cannons of Orissa Architecture are yet to be found; information available in these books are valuable resources that can contribute much to enable the digital preservation and promotion of Odisha's tangible and intangible

Conclusion

In India, the ultimate temple, since times ancient, has always been the human body. To inhabit the human body was to inhabit the structure of the universe. A line of seers and sages of various communities dating back through the Vedic period and beyond, arrived at this conclusion through evolving philosophic speculations and ritual traditions. The Rig Veda referred to cosmic construction as comparable to the construction of a house. And it is in the Atharva Veda that cosmic speculation and the human body were brought into a formal homology. Temple Hinduism, however, did not begin as a system of worship until the 1st century AD according to some scholars, yet it was built on the foundation of cosmological and semantic interpretation that preceded it. Thus, the Hindu temple is perceived as a link between man and God, between the earthly life and divine life, between the actual and the ideal.

The most vital part of a Hindu temple is its Garbha Gruha or the sanctum sanctorum. It is the centre of all energy and derives its name from the 'garbha' or womb of a mother wherein rests the 'praana' or the life of creation. And it is surrounding this garbha that the entire temple structure is visualised and constructed. The temple also represents God himself, in a cosmic form, with the various worlds located on different parts of His body. The bhuloka (earth) forms His feet and Satyaloka (also called Brahmaloaka or heaven) forms His shikhar with the other lokas Bhuvar, Svar, Mahar, Jnyana, Tapa represented by the adhishtanapitha or the base slab below the mutri, the stambhas or the pillars, the prastara or entablature above the pillars, amalsara or lower part of the finial and stupika or topknot of the finial respectively. Again, the temple represents this world in all its aspects, the actual and the ideal. The imposing gopapurams at the entrance reflect the magnificent grandeur of the exterior world. The friezes and sculptures on the external walls of the temple depict the animal world as also the myriad lived of ordinary people including the maithuna figures, of couples closely embracing or actually *in coitu*, which are obviously connected with fertility and are considered auspicious. More often, they are iconographical representations of creation and of the bipolar nature of this creative world, which is described in the philosophical treatises as arising out of the union of Purusha (spirit) and Prakruti (nature). Many suggestions have been made as to the true significance of these figures; it has been suggested that they merely served the mundane purpose of advertising the charms of the devadasis, or temple dancers, or that they were intended to represent the world of the flesh, in contrast to the bare and austere interior, which symbolised the things of the spirit; possibly they were connected, in the minds of their designers, with sexual mysticism which played so great a part in medieval Indian religious thought, or it may be that they represent the delights of heaven, on its lower planes. These are followed by scenes from epics and mythologies, as also religious

symbols and icons of gods and goddesses, to remind the onlookers of our rich cultural, philosophical and religious heritage.

As a representation of the human body itself, the various parts of the body of the temple are named in accordance with the different parts of the human body: Paada (foot) is the base, Jangha (shank) is part of the superstructure over the base, Galaa or Grivaa (neck) is the part between mouldings at the top resembling the neck, while Garbhagruha represents the heart and the image, the Antaryamin or the indwelling lord. This symbology attempts to impress upon man the need to seek God within and not outside one's own self.

The temple also represents the subtle body (Sukshma sharira) with the seven psychic centres called chakras. The Garbhagruha represents the Anaahata Chakra (fourth chakra in the heart region) and the Kalasha apex represents the Sahasraara (seventh chakra at the crown of the head). The first three chakras – Muladhaara, Svaadhishthaana and Manipura near the anus, sex organ and navel respectively, are below the ground of the temple while the fifth and sixth chakras at the throat and between the eyebrows respectively, Vishuddha and Ajna are located in the shikhara section of the temple.

Very often, the ground plan of a Hindu temple is a mandala which is a geometric diagram with occult potentialities. Symmetry is its chief characteristic. The created world which is a perfect handicraft of a perfectionist, the Creator himself, can be best represented by a symmetrical and well proportioned mandala, The movement in it, so far as the devotee is concerned, is from the outer details to the inner centre which is a point. This point represents the one and only Creative Principle, the Deity, the Universal Truth, from which everything has evolved. Thus the Hindu temple is a symbol of the physical, physio-psychical and the metaphysical planes of the human body and mind.

Mano Mohan Ganguly in his *Orissa and Her Remains* traces the political, religious, socio-economic history of Orissa and its impact on Orissan art and architecture in great detail. Of particular interest is the chapter on Temples of Bhubanesvara, which is also relevant to this study, where he gives detailed accounts of all the aforementioned temples. He also gives detailed drawings of the temple and site plans which offer important reference points.

Nirmal Kumar Bose in *Cannons of Orissan Architecture* states his book to be a continuation of the accounts afforded by Ganguly. He begins with the four approaches to Indian architecture and continues to explain the relevance of local science of architecture to the understanding and appreciation of Indian Architecture in general and Orissan Architecture in particular. The details so given as regards the indigenous methods of recording building details speaks much of the intangible aspect of Indian architecture that needs adequate study and analysis for due appreciation and record.

Stella Kramrisch in *The Hindu Temple* draws parallel between the temple structure and the human body, likens the temple to the Cosmic Man or Purusha and brings together art, philosophy and science together on the same plane and platform for further contemplation and analysis.

Alice Boner in *Shilpa Prakasha* states the author of this text, who gives his name as Ramachandra Bhattaraka was an Orissan architect living in a tantric village. As a follower of the Kaulachara doctrine he worshipped Jagannatha under the name of Dakshina Kalika. A distinctive feature of S.P. is the method followed in the outlay of the groundplan of temple and mukhashala, starting from the centre of the garbhagrha, and growing outwards in geometrical proportions based on units of measurement underlying the grabhagrha. Under the grabhagrha a Yogini yantra has to be consecrated, which also does not occur in other Shilpa Shastras.

Kapila Vatsyayan in *Classical Indian Dance in Literature and the Arts* explains the interdisciplinary system within which classical arts of India, be it architecture, sculpture, dance, music, painting, are embedded such that they together form an organic whole like the various branches of the same tree. That science in sculpture making, the technology in temple building, the grammar of Indian classical dance which borrows heavily from the former two, are interlinked by a continuous invisible thread is brought to the fore by Vatsyayan aesthetically and scientifically.

Gazetteer of India gives a fair record of Orissan architecture, highlighting the important temples of Bhubaneswar.

Finally, *Digital Hampi* brings a fresh approach to how we perceive heritage and opens our eyes to the numerous possibilities that modern technology brings to us in digitally preserving and promoting Indian cultural heritage. *Digital Hampi* thus attempts to bridge culture and technology.

Regarding the nature of Indian art, A K Coomaraswamy wrote in 1923:

‘The memory picture- or rather, a synthetic image based on past experience- is from first to last the essential foundation of Indian art.....The Indian method is always one of visualisation – unconscious in primitive, systematised in the mature art. Indian art is always a language employing symbols, valid only by tradition and convention’¹⁷.

Digital Hampi attempts to capture this memory picture or synthetic image that leads to the tangible and intangible in Indian art and architecture through highly advanced modern science and technology such that this memory picture is not lost but is rediscovered, nurtured virtually and

¹⁷ Coomaraswamy, Ananda *The Transformation of Nature in Indian Art* (1934) 12pp

made accessible to future generations across the world, anytime, anywhere through the World Wide Web.

References

- Boner & Sharma, Alicia & Sadashiv Ratha. *Shilpa Prakasha*. Leiden, Netherlands: E J Brill, 1966.
- Bose, Nirmal Kumar. *Cannons of Orissan Architecture*. Calcutta: R Chatterjee, 1932.
- Chopra, Dr. P N. *The Gazetteer of India*. New Delhi: Publications Division, Ministry of Information & Broadcasting, Govt of India, 1973.
- Ganguly, O C. *Orissa and Her Remains - Ancient and Medieval*. Calcutta, London: Thacker Spin & Co, W. Thacker & Co, 1912.
- Kramrisch, Stella. *The Hindu Temple*. University of Calcutta, 1946.
- Mallik, Anupama, et al. *Digital Hampi: Preserving Indian Cultural Heritage*. Singapore: Springer, 2017.
- . *Digital Hampi: Preserving Indian Cultural Heritage*. Singapore: Springer, 2017.
- Vatsyayan, Kapila. *Classical Indian Dance in Literature and the Arts*. New Delhi: Sangeet Natak Akademi, 1968.
- . *Evidence of Odissi in Indian Miniatures*. Mumbai: Marg Publications, 1960.